

Physical Layer Authentication With Transmit-Controlled Channel

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Abstract—This paper proposes a physical layer authentication (PLA) scheme for downlink cellular systems in which the transmitter controls the channel via a reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS). The receiver first learns the channel responses associated with all RIS configurations. During data transmission, the transmitter encodes messages by randomly selecting a public codeword that specifies a sequence of RIS configurations. Authentication is performed by comparing the estimated channel sequence with that expected from the decoded codeword. The tradeoff between communication performance and security is analyzed in terms of channel capacity and false alarm (FA) and missed detection (MD) probabilities. Both hard and soft decoding strategies are considered, and numerical results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed scheme in improving downlink security.

Index Terms—Authentication, Challenge-response, Intelligent Reflecting Surfaces, Downlink.

I. INTRODUCTION

Source authentication refers to verifying whether a received message genuinely originates from the declared sender or has been forged by an attacker. Physical layer authentication (PLA) leverages the unique characteristics of the wireless propagation channel as a device or link signature. The fundamental PLA approach, introduced by Simmons [1], involves two phases: an *association phase*, where the receiver (Bob) estimates the channel using signals sent by the legitimate transmitter (Alice), typically authenticated via higher-layer protocols; and a *verification phase*, where Bob estimates the channel for each newly received message and compares it against the reference from the first phase. Consistency between these estimates, accounting for noise, indicates that the message is authentic. Comprehensive surveys on PLA can be found in [2], [3]. Recently, channel control techniques have been studied via reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) composed of passive reflecting elements [4], which can be configured to improve signal quality and mitigate impairments [5], [6].

Challenge-response (CR)-based PLA is a security protocol that can be employed when the receiver (verifier) controls the channel (e.g., by configuring a RIS). In CR-PLA, the verifier sends a challenge selected from a predefined set to the transmitter to confirm authenticity [1]. The general CR-PLA framework can be applied in both uplink and downlink

scenarios, differing mainly in which entity controls the RIS. In the uplink case, studied in [7], the receiver (Bob) controls the RIS, configuring it while the transmitter (Alice) sends authenticated pilot signals. Bob estimates the channel for each configuration during association and verifies authenticity by comparing new channel estimates with stored ones in the verification phase.

This paper proposes a PLA mechanism in which a *legitimate transmitter controls the channel by configuring an RIS, while the receiver performs authentication*. Unlike CR-PLA, where channel control must be exercised by the receiver, our approach considers a previously unexplored scenario in which channel control and authentication are carried out by two distinct entities. The proposed mechanism operates in two stages. First, the receiver learns the channel responses associated with all possible RIS configurations. Then, the transmitter randomly selects a codeword from a public codebook, whose symbols specify a sequence of RIS configurations used to transmit the data packets forming a message. The receiver estimates the channel for each packet and identifies the most likely RIS configuration sequence using the channel knowledge acquired in the first phase. The message is authenticated if the resulting channel sequence closely matches that associated with the decoded codeword. Two decoding strategies, hard and soft decoding, are examined.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the system model and attacker capabilities. Section IV presents the proposed authentication mechanism. Section III provides the details of the verification phase. Numerical results from MATLAB simulations are given in Section V, followed by concluding remarks in Section VI.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider the communication scenario shown in Fig. 1, where a receiver Bob (the user) seeks to authenticate a message from a legitimate transmitter Alice (the base-station (BS)), while an attacker, Trudy, attempts to impersonate Alice by sending forged messages. All devices are assumed to be equipped with a single antenna.

We assume that Alice controls a RIS with N reflecting elements with unit gain and introducing phase shifts $\phi_n = e^{j\theta_n}$, for $n = 1, \dots, N$ on the baseband signal. We define

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Fig. 1. Communication scenario.

a *configuration* as the vector $\phi = [\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_N]^T$ and the corresponding diagonal matrix

$$\Phi = \text{diag}\{\phi\} = \text{diag}\{\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_N\}. \quad (1)$$

Such a scenario differs from CR-PLA, where the RIS (thus the channel) is controlled by the receiver. The RIS configuration maximizing the capacity of the cascaded channel is defined as

$$\Phi^* = \text{diag}\{e^{j\theta_1^*}, \dots, e^{j\theta_N^*}\}. \quad (2)$$

In our single-antenna scenario, the optimal communication configuration provides

$$\theta_n^* = \alpha - \angle h_n - \angle g_n, \quad n = 1, \dots, N, \quad (3)$$

where $\angle h_n$ and $\angle g_n$ are the phases of the n -th elements of the channels \mathbf{h} and \mathbf{g} , respectively, and α is a common phase applied to all RIS elements.

Set of RIS Configurations: We consider here that Alice can use only M RIS configurations, denoted by ϕ_1, \dots, ϕ_M , generated starting from the optimal communication configuration Φ^* . For each configuration ϕ_m , the phase shift introduced by the n -th reflecting element of the RIS is defined as

$$\phi_{m,n} = e^{j(\theta_n^* + \epsilon_{m,n})}, \quad m = 1, \dots, M, \quad n = 1, \dots, N, \quad (4)$$

where $\epsilon_{m,n} \sim \mathcal{U}[-\gamma, \gamma]$ is a uniformly distributed random perturbation. The parameter γ controls the maximum deviation introduced with respect to the optimal configuration.

Alice-Bob Channel: We assume that communication between Alice and Bob occurs exclusively via the RIS, with no direct link between them. The baseband equivalent channels from Alice to the RIS and from the RIS to Bob are defined as $\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times N}$, respectively. Thus, the resulting Alice-RIS-Bob cascaded channel is

$$q = \mathbf{h}\Phi\mathbf{g} \in \mathbb{C}. \quad (5)$$

A. Attacker Model

The goal of Trudy is to impersonate the legitimate transmitter Alice and pass the authentication test performed by the receiver Bob. It is assumed that Trudy has no control over the RIS, and to deceive Bob, she is equipped with a large antenna array, allowing her to induce any desired channel estimate at the receiver.

We assume that Trudy may transmit messages to Bob through a direct channel. The channels \mathbf{h} and \mathbf{g} are assumed to be time-invariant and reciprocal, but since the RIS configuration is controlled by Alice and can be changed over time, the cascaded channel q is partially controllable.

Trudy is assumed to have *partial knowledge* of the cascaded channel. Specifically, she is assumed to know perfectly the channel \mathbf{h} between the RIS and Bob. This assumption is justified by Trudy's proximity to Bob, which enables her to estimate this portion of the channel accurately. Additionally, Trudy has an imperfect estimate of the channel \mathbf{g} between Alice and the RIS, modeled as

$$\mathbf{z} = \rho\mathbf{g} + \sqrt{1 - \rho^2}\mathbf{d}, \quad (6)$$

where $\rho \in [0, 1]$ is the correlation coefficient between \mathbf{z} and the true channel \mathbf{g} . The entries of \mathbf{d} are independent, zero-mean, unit-variance complex Gaussian random variables, independent also of \mathbf{g} and \mathbf{h} .

III. PROPOSED AUTHENTICATION MECHANISM

In the proposed authentication method, Alice will transmit a message split into F packets, each transmitted using a different RIS configuration. The sequence of RIS configurations used to transmit a message is denoted as a *codeword* and is randomly selected from a codebook. Note that such a random sequence is not supposed to carry any information, but is chosen here for authentication purposes only. However, Alice can also transmit data with such a sequence. What matters for authentication is that it is selected (uniformly) random from the codebook.

A. Codebook Design

As introduced in the previous Section in (4), M RIS configurations are available, thus the symbols of each codeword are taken from the alphabet $\{1, \dots, M\}$, and do not carry explicit information on the resulting Alice-Bob channels. Thus, the knowledge of the codebook by Trudy does not imply her knowledge of the cascade channel q for the various configurations. The codebook is denoted as

$$\mathcal{C} = \{\mathbf{c}_1, \mathbf{c}_2, \dots, \mathbf{c}_S\}, \quad |\mathcal{C}| = S, \quad (7)$$

where each codeword \mathbf{c}_i , for $i = 1, \dots, S$, identifies a sequence of F RIS configurations. In particular, the i -th sequence can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{c}_i = [c_{i,1}, c_{i,2}, \dots, c_{i,F}], \quad (8)$$

where $c_{i,j} \in \{1, \dots, M\}$ represents the index of one of the M available RIS configurations, with $i = 1, \dots, S$ and $j = 1, \dots, F$. Note that the codebook has $|\mathcal{C}| < M^F$ sequences, thus not all RIS configuration sequences of length F are valid codewords.

B. PLA Mechanism

In detail, the proposed PLA mechanism comprises two phases: the association phase and the verification phase. The association phase is performed only once, while the verification phase is repeated upon transmission of any new message.

Fig. 2. Message structure.

Association Phase: During the *association* phase, Alice transmits a sequence of pilot symbols using the M RIS configurations $\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_M$, generated according to (4). For each configuration ϕ_m , Alice sets the RIS and transmits known pilot symbols. Upon reception, Bob estimates the resulting cascade channel $\bar{q}_m \in \mathbb{C}$ corresponding to the current configuration as

$$\bar{q}_m = q_m + w, \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M, \quad (9)$$

where w denotes the estimation error at the receiver, modeled as zero-mean additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with variance σ^2 . After each transmission, Alice updates the RIS configuration to ϕ_{m+1} and repeats the process. At the end of the association phase, Bob has collected the estimates \bar{q}_m for all configurations $m = 1, \dots, M$. These complex estimates compose a constellation of points representing the different channel estimates associated with each configuration.

Verification Phase: The verification phase is here outlined and then described in more detail in Section IV. Alice splits the message into F frames. Then, she selects a sequence $c_i \in \mathcal{C}$, with $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, S\}$. Such a sequence is selected for authentication purposes, but it may also carry information to be transferred to the receiver. The F configuration indices $c_{i,j}$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, F$, from the i -th sequence are then assigned to the corresponding message frames. Each frame is therefore transmitted using a different RIS configuration, following the order in c_i . Fig. 2 illustrates the message structure: each of the F frames consists of a pilot (in gray) and a data section. The configuration ϕ_{m_j} is shown below the corresponding frame.

Upon receiving the j -th frame, with $j = 1, \dots, F$, Bob exploits the known pilot symbols to estimate the cascade channel \hat{q}_j . After receiving all F frames, Bob has the sequence $\hat{\mathbf{q}} = [\hat{q}_1, \hat{q}_2, \dots, \hat{q}_F]$ of channel estimates. Then, using the information gathered during the association phase, Bob maps each estimate \hat{q}_j to the corresponding RIS configuration index, yielding the estimated sequence $\hat{\mathbf{c}} = [\hat{c}_1, \hat{c}_2, \dots, \hat{c}_F]$. The method used for this mapping will be discussed in Section IV.

Bob's goal is to determine whether the estimated sequence $\hat{\mathbf{c}}$ corresponds to one of the predefined sequences $c_i \in \mathcal{C}$, for $i = 1, \dots, S$. To this end, Bob performs an authentication test, deciding between the following hypotheses: \mathcal{H}_0 : The message originates from Alice; \mathcal{H}_1 : The message originates from Trudy.

C. Attack Strategy

Trudy is assumed to know the public codebook \mathcal{C} shared by Alice and Bob. Hence, she forges a message to Bob that appears to have passed through a channel using a valid sequence of RIS configurations. However, Trudy does not have a perfect estimate of the channel \mathbf{g} , thus she cannot reproduce the effect of the true Alice-Bob cascaded channel.

Fig. 3. Block diagram of Alice and Bob devices.

IV. VERIFICATION PHASE

This Section describes the verification phase, when Bob evaluates the authenticity of the received message. The operations performed by Alice and Bob in this phase are shown in the block diagram of Fig. 3.

Alice Transmission: Alice selects the sequence of RIS configurations by generating uniformly at random the binary string $\mathbf{u} \in \{0, 1\}^{\log_2 S}$. The encoder then maps \mathbf{u} to the codeword $c_b \in \mathcal{C}$. Each RIS configuration in c_b is used when transmitting a message frame. Note that we are modulating the binary string \mathbf{u} into a sequence of RIS configurations: this can also be done to transmit a message to Bob with \mathbf{u} , but here we focus on its use for authentication only.

Channel Estimation: Upon reception, Bob uses the known pilot symbols in each frame to obtain a *channel estimate* for each of the F received frames. The estimate for the j -th frame, denoted $\hat{q}_j \in \mathbb{C}$, is associated with the configuration ϕ_{c_j} used during transmission and is modeled as

$$\hat{q}_j = \mathbf{h}\Phi_{c_j}\mathbf{g} + \hat{w}, \quad (10)$$

where \hat{w} is the estimation noise, modeled as zero-mean AWGN with variance $\hat{\sigma}^2$. After receiving all frames, Bob forms the full estimate vector $\hat{\mathbf{q}} = [\hat{q}_1, \dots, \hat{q}_F]$.

Sequence Demodulation: In the *demodulation phase*, each \hat{q}_j is compared with the M reference values \bar{q}_m , $m = 1, \dots, M$, from the association phase. The demodulator (DEMOD) assigns to each \hat{q}_j the index \hat{m}_j of the closest point in the constellation. These indices are concatenated into the demodulated RIS configuration sequence $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_b$. This sequence is then passed to the *decoding phase*. The decoder (DECOD) takes $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_b$ as input and returns an estimate of the original message, denoted $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$.

Authentication Step: Bob determines whether the message originates from a legitimate transmitter or an attacker by comparing a decision metric Ψ against a threshold τ

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi < \tau &: \hat{\mathcal{H}} = \mathcal{H}_0, \\ \Psi \geq \tau &: \hat{\mathcal{H}} = \mathcal{H}_1. \end{aligned}$$

Two different criteria for computing Ψ are considered in the following: *hard* and *soft* verification metrics. In both cases, Bob obtains $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ from decoding; the difference lies in how the metric Ψ is defined.

A. Hard Metric Verification

In the hard metric approach, Ψ is computed from \hat{c}_b , derived by associating each \hat{q}_j with the closest \bar{q}_m in the constellation, without considering the distance values themselves. This corresponds to a hard quantization of the channel estimates: each \hat{q}_j is uniquely assigned to a known configuration $\phi_{\hat{m}_j}$ based on minimum distance. Concatenating the indices yields \hat{c}_b .

The metric Ψ is then the Hamming distance between \hat{c}_b and the codeword $f_{\text{ENC}}(\hat{u})$:

$$\Psi = d_{\text{H}}(\hat{c}_b, f_{\text{ENC}}(\hat{u})), \quad (11)$$

where $d_{\text{H}}(\cdot, \cdot)$ denotes the Hamming distance and $f_{\text{ENC}}(\cdot)$ is the encoding function. A small Ψ indicates a high consistency with a valid codeword, suggesting legitimate transmission; a large Ψ suggests a potential attack.

B. Soft Metric Verification

In the soft metric approach, Ψ accounts for actual distances between the received estimates and the reference points.

Bob first reconstructs the codeword $f_{\text{ENC}}(\hat{u})$ and obtains the corresponding RIS configuration sequence. The associated channel estimates from the reference constellation form the vector $\bar{\mathbf{q}} = [\bar{q}_1, \dots, \bar{q}_F]$. This is compared to the received estimate vector $\hat{\mathbf{q}} = [\hat{q}_1, \dots, \hat{q}_F]$. A natural consistency measure is the mean Euclidean distance¹:

$$\Psi = d_M = \frac{1}{F} \sum_{j=1}^F |\hat{q}_j - \bar{q}_j|, \quad (12)$$

which captures the average deviation in the complex plane.

C. On The RIS Configuration and Channel Capacity

When generating the set of RIS configurations according to (4), the choice of the parameter γ directly impacts the trade-off between communication performance and authentication robustness. For a given RIS configuration ϕ_m , the instantaneous signal to noise ratio (SNR) at the receiver is given by

$$\omega_m = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \left| \sum_{n=1}^N h_n g_n e^{j(\theta_n^* + \varepsilon_{m,n})} \right|^2, \quad (13)$$

and the corresponding achievable rate is $C_m = \log_2(1 + \omega_m)$. In the large- N regime, the resulting average SNR $\Omega = \mathbb{E}[\omega_m]$ depends on the phase perturbation distribution only through the parameter $\mu = \mathbb{E}[e^{j\varepsilon_{m,n}}] = \mathbb{E}[\cos \varepsilon_{m,n}]$ [8, sec. IIIA], which for uniformly distributed perturbations $\varepsilon_{m,n} \sim \mathcal{U}[-\gamma, \gamma]$ evaluates to $\mu = \sin(\gamma)/\gamma$. Under this assumption, the average SNR is approximated as

$$\Omega \approx \frac{N}{\sigma^2} \left((N-1) \frac{\pi^2}{16} \mu^2 + 1 \right), \quad (14)$$

which scales proportionally to μ^2 . Consequently, while larger values of γ enhance the randomness of the observed channel

¹This soft metric offers a continuous measure of similarity between the estimated and expected channel responses, potentially enhancing sensitivity to small deviations introduced by an attacker compared to the hard approach.

realizations and thus improve the system's ability to distinguish legitimate transmissions from forged ones, they degrade the achievable rate through a reduction of Ω .

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section presents the numerical results of the security and communication performance of the proposed techniques. The RIS configuration codebook has been obtained from a low-density parity check (LDPC) codebook, mapping groups of binary symbols into M -ary symbols, each representing one of the M RIS configurations. Thus, for encoding and decoding, state-of-the-art procedures for LDPC codes are used.

Performance is evaluated as a function of the parameter $[\Lambda]_{\text{dB}} = -10 \log_{10} \hat{\sigma}^2$, where $\hat{\sigma}^2$ represents the variance of the AWGN noise observed at the receiver during the verification phase. In contrast, perfect channel knowledge is assumed for Bob during the association phase. The number of reflecting elements of the RIS is $N = 32$ in all scenarios. The number of configurations, M , is varied, while the number of frames transmitted by Alice, F , is held constant.

In the following, the performance of the system under both *hard decoding* and *soft decoding* will be analyzed.

A. Hard Decoding

In the case of *hard decoding*, discussed in Section IV-A, the authentication metric defined in (11) is used. This metric corresponds to the Hamming distance between \hat{c}_b and the codeword associated with the sequence \hat{u} decided by Bob.

Fig. 4 shows the detection error tradeoff (DET) curves obtained for different values of ρ (cf. (6)). As expected, the DET curves corresponding to $\rho = 1$ and $\rho = 0.999$ are nearly overlapping. This reflects the attacker's high ability to emulate the legitimate transmitter when the channel correlation is extremely high. For $\rho = 0.997$, the curve shows a noticeable improvement in detection performance, indicating an increased separability between legitimate and forged messages. Interestingly, for lower values of correlation, such as $\rho = 0.9$ and $\rho = 0.3$, the DET curves start to converge again. This effect can be attributed to the saturation of the Hamming distance: as the correlation drops, the attacker's signal becomes increasingly uncorrelated with the legitimate one, and the expected Hamming distance tends toward half the codeword length. This results in a reduced impact of further decreasing ρ on the authentication performance.

Overall, the results highlight that even small deviations from perfect channel knowledge ($\rho < 1$) can lead to significantly improved authentication capabilities. However, this benefit saturates as ρ decreases below a certain threshold.

B. Soft Decoding

In the case of *soft decoding*, the authentication metric defined in (12) is used. This metric corresponds to the average Euclidean distance, computed frame by frame, between the received channel estimates and those associated with the decoded codebook sequence.

Fig. 4. Comparison of DET curves for hard decoding with different values of ρ , with $N = 32$, $M = 256$, $S = 128$, $F = 10$, $\gamma = \frac{\pi}{2}$, $[\Lambda]_{\text{dB}} = 10$ dB, $N_{\text{iter}} = 10^5$, and $n = 80$ bit.

Fig. 5. Comparison of DET curves for soft decoding with different values of ρ , with $N = 32$, $M = 256$, $S = 128$, $F = 10$, $[\Lambda]_{\text{dB}} = 10$ dB, $N_{\text{iter}} = 10^5$, $\gamma = \frac{\pi}{2}$, and $n = 80$ bit.

Fig. 5 shows the DET curves obtained with soft decoding for various values of ρ . As the correlation decreases, both the false alarm (FA) and missed detection (MD) probabilities improve significantly. This trend contrasts with the behavior observed for hard decoding in Fig. 4, where performance tends to saturate as ρ becomes smaller. Moreover, comparing the DET curves obtained for hard decoding in Fig. 4, with those for soft decoding in Fig. 5, we note that, for high values of ρ (above 0.9), both decoding strategies yield comparable authentication performance. This is because, in such conditions, Trudy is able to emulate Alice's channel with high precision, leading Bob to produce channel estimates that are nearly indistinguishable from the legitimate ones. As the correlation coefficient ρ decreases, the differences between hard and soft decoding become increasingly evident. This is due to the reduced similarity between the legitimate and forged channel estimates: soft decoding, which exploits the Euclidean structure of the estimates, becomes more effective in distinguishing between authentic and malicious signals.

Fig. 6 illustrates the tradeoff between Ω and p_{MD} for different values of p_{FA} and soft decoding strategy. For instance, the angles $\gamma = \pi/2, \pi/3$, and $\pi/6$ correspond to $\Omega = 34.47$,

Fig. 6. p_{MD} as a function of Ω for different values of the p_{FA} for soft decoding, with $N = 32$, $M = 256$, $S = 128$, $F = 10$, $[\Lambda]_{\text{dB}} = 10$ dB, and $n = 80$ bit.

36.54, and 37.71 dB, respectively, as given by (14). For a fixed p_{FA} , increasing Ω leads to a higher p_{MD} , highlighting the inherent compromise between security and communication performance. Moreover, larger values of p_{FA} enable a lower minimum achievable p_{MD} .

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed and analyzed a PLA scheme for downlink wireless communications using a RIS controlled by the transmitting BS. The authentication mechanism relies on multiple RIS configurations per message, with the configuration sequence generated through an encoding procedure. Two decoding strategies, hard and soft, were investigated, each with a dedicated authentication metric. Simulation results validate the proposed model and reveal a tradeoff between communication performance and security. The system effectively distinguishes legitimate transmitters from attackers, with soft decoding providing improved robustness.

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